

HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY: A PERSPECTIVE OF INDIAN PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

In ancient India, indigenous education was imparted at Chatuspathis and Gurukuls. Ancient Indian Education was dominated by strict moral codes of conduct. Learners used to accomplish self-reverence, self-knowledge and self-control, which lead to the transformation in life. The actual meaning of education was self-culture and self-realization - the realization of the ultimate truth. 'Personality' means a combination of values which form the distinct character of man. How learners of ancient India inculcated humane values from their Acharyas which helped them to develop their holistic personality is the theme that has unfolded in this academic endeavour.

Keywords: Pedagogy, Ethology, Oral transmission of knowledge, Memorisation, Oral repetition, Parable-telling, Monophobia, Divinity, Animal-man, Convocation

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Pedagogy is widely used in the sense of the 'Science of Teaching'. Teaching is a process of contribution to the growth of knowledge, skill, literature or art, etc. It is an activity to train the students for creative thinking to face the challenges in their future lives. Pedagogy, in the area of educational sciences, plays an important role with regard to elevating the all-round development of the learners. In the ancient Indian educational system, Pedagogy was there. However, it was not considered distinctly and separately in education. After the introduction of Modern Education in India by the Europeans, Pedagogy was considered to be the most essential component in the teaching-learning process and teachers today have been ensuing contemporary methods of teaching, which are said to have evolved in the Western countries. But it is a pang of conscience that we seldom search for such a fundamentally indigenous philosophy of learning and teaching, which evolved in India long back. So it is crucial to explore Indian Pedagogy enshrined in the ancient Indian Education System.

SIGNIFICANCE OF INDIAN PEDAGOGY

Each country has its own Philosophy of Education. Unlike the educational philosophies of Greece and China, which separated Education and Religion, in the Indian educational philosophy, the two were intertwined. On analysing the Pedagogy of ancient India, it may be said that developing character was more important in India than enhancing intellect. In the ancient Indian education system, "culture, not literacy, was the highest aim of Education" (Venketeswara, 1980, pp. 240-241). This core area of educational philosophy has been reflected in the ancient

Indian teaching-learning process. If we do a careful and exhaustive investigation of the ancient Indian teaching process with an objective of advancing knowledge, we will find a lot of basic teaching principles which are being placed as the primary tenets of Indian Pedagogy. The key characteristics of Indian Pedagogy are *oral transmission of knowledge, teacher-questioning, memorisation, oral repetition, parable-telling, etc.*, that have been used since the Vedic times.

One of the most important epicenters of ancient Indian education was Nabadwip, and the traditional education system was patronized by the Maharaja of Nadia. In the time of Raja Rudra of A.D. 1680, the numbers of students learning at Nabadwip were 4,000 and the numbers of teachers were 600. These numbers are a testimony to the excellence of the academic culture of the then Nabadwip. The learning centres where such academic excellence blossomed were known as Chatuspathis ('schools' in modern terminology). It appears that all these schools were for advanced Sanskrit studies and that students seeking them spent nearly twenty years at these schools. They generally got by heart the texts they studied. These schools conducted classes in the form of seminars or colloquiums, where two teachers would start a debate on an abstruse topic, which the students had to follow and supplement with their own questions. The advancement of knowledge by means of learned open debates had been India's indigenous method of education through the ages. (Mookherji, 2022, p. 601)

AIMS OF EDUCATION IN ANCIENT INDIA

Building the character of the students was one of the most important aims of Education during the age of the Upanishads. 'Character-training', in fact, means the training of the will, which is the mental force. The willpower must be strengthened and properly directed, which is possible through the practice of concentration, self-control, and culture of refined and lofty sentiments. The willpower of the students was strengthened and also directed towards good things alone, while they lived in the house of their preceptors. There, they had to live as Brahmacharins, who, besides their daily duties, had to practice concentration, self-control and training of the sentiments. During the period of studentship they were to sincerely practice (Taittiriya Upanishad, 1. 9. 1):

- i. Righteousness
- ii. Truth
- iii. Austerity

The students had to live under the direct supervision of their preceptors, who were held responsible not only for their intellectual progress but also for their psychophysical acts. The severe rules which they had to follow in the preceptors' house were to develop their character in such a way that they could become pure in their ideas, words and deeds. Their everyday lives followed the etiquettes and good manners towards their elders, equals and juniors. They were trained to become well-adjusted members of the society and also to be gainfully employed in various works on the completion of their education.

UNIVERSALISATION THROUGH SELF-REALISATION: AN UNIQUE APPROACH OF ANCIENT INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

The chief goal of the ancient Indian education system was 'Self-realisation'. Self-realisation springs from the resolute practice of a lot of good habits. Residential learners were not only imparted mere lessons by their Acharyas but also directed to follow a set of good habits so that they can become healthier, saner and integrated members of the society. Through education, the learners were inspired by their preceptors that they have 'Divinity' within themselves. At the same time they were provided the training of unselfishness. How to achieve adaptive behaviour, how to work and live together - learners used to follow such core human values, instructed by their facilitators. Indian Pedagogy did not mean letting people know what they know, but teaching people to behave how they do not behave. In ancient India, through taking lessons from Acharyas, learners achieved those values, which can be defined operationally to include norms of right conduct, good intellectual and moral habits.

Today, at the dawn of economic globalisation, when education has become a commodity, its goal is to be a useful citizen. But the aim of the ancient Indian Education system was Self-realization, to be concerned for others, to become an Universal Being. In this perspective, we can mention that Indian Pedagogy (Science of Teaching) and Ethology (Science of Character), go hand in hand. We must retrospect our ancient Indian Education System. We must try to understand the current Education System with reference to the past.

PRINCIPLES OF STUDENTSHIP

In ancient India, the period of studentship was considered as a preparatory period for the gaining of the knowledge of the Absolute. When the students would graduate, thus beginning a new journey after having gone through years of rigorous schooling, the teachers would offer some invaluable Principles that they were supposed to follow throughout their lives:

First Principle

शरीरमाद्यं खलु धर्मसाधनम् - इति नीतिवाक्यमवधार्य श्रमक्षमनीरोगशीराय
स्वास्थ्यविधिपालनपरो भवितुमहं यथासाध्यं यतिष्ये। (कुमारसम्भवम्, यत्र शिवपार्वतयोः)

Literal meaning

This body is the only means to spiritual practice. From an educational perspective, the body is the only instrument to achieve all kinds of knowledge.

Social Interpretation and Significance

The primary existence of human life springs from the body with its multiorgan structure. We should keep it in order. Though we know the body is ephemeral, not permanent, yet, we can never ignore it. We have come to know from modern science the two parts of the structural body of a computer. It has hardware, which is the outer physical structure and software, which is the locomotive force of the unit. Though software is the key concern of the machine, hardware is the supporting container to functioning software. Like this, though the human body is ephemeral, and the human mind is the chief concern to know everything, to achieve knowledge,

the mind exists in the body. For achieving knowledge we need a sound mind, and a sound mind rests in sound health. If health is not in order, the mind will be unable to act properly, because we have a body-mind complex. So, we should keep and protect this gross body properly by providing necessary nutritious food, physical movement (exercise) and needful rest. For the holistic development of the personality, physical awareness and protection of the learners is urgently needed. This was mentioned in our ancient Indian education system, following the teaching of Upanishad; and its present-day relevance is accepted by all stakeholders of Education (administrators, teachers, learners, guardians and community).

Second Principle

छात्राणामध्ययनं तपः - इति स्मृतिवाक्यमवधार्य प्रतिभाविकाशार्थमाचारनिरतोऽध्ययनपरो भवितुमहं यथासाध्यं यतिष्ये। (छान्दोग्योपनिषत् - २.२३.१)

Literal Meaning

It simply means that learning is the fundamental task of learners. Persevering incessantly is the virtue of learners.

Social Interpretation and Significance

Continuous persevering with patience is the key concern for the success of learners. According to the educational philosophy of Swami Vivekananda, all knowledge exists in our mind, and the learner has to uncover it by his own effort. Sister Nivedita, in her famous book 'Religion and Dharma' (1915), in the chapter 'The Teacher' (pp. 73-76), tried to focus the views of Swamiji on teachers, pointing out that the true teacher knows that no one can really aid another. All that a teacher can do is to stimulate the learner to help himself, and remove from his path the real obstacles to his doing so. In this perspective, we have come to know that in Education, teachers act as facilitators and counsellors to help the learners so that they can express or manifest their potential within themselves. The learners' own effort, struggle, and perseverance is urgently needed to bring success.

Though attentive learning is the tapas or austerity of the learners, they also have another three kinds of tapas/austerity to practice, which have been enshrined in Bhagavad Gita. Verses 14-16 of the 17th chapter of Gita mentions austerity of body, austerity of speech and austerity of the mind :

(1) देवद्रिजगुरुप्राश्रपूजनं शौचमार्जवम्।
ब्रह्मचर्यमहिंसा च शारीरं तप उच्यते॥ १४

i.e., to pay deep regards to Gods, Acharyas, Guru and Wise, cleanliness, straightforwardness, continence and non-injury are called the austerity of the body.

(2) अनुद्वेगकरं वाक्यं सत्यं प्रियहितं च यत्।
स्वाध्यायाभ्यसनं चैव वाङ्मयं तप उच्यते॥ १५

i.e., speech which causes no vexation and which is true as also agreeable and beneficial and regular study of the holy texts— these are said to form the austerity of speech.

(3) मनः प्रसादः सौम्यत्वं मौनमात्मविनिग्रहः ।
भावसंशुद्धिरित्येतन्नपो मानसमुच्यते ॥ १६

i.e., Serenity of mind, kindness, silence, self-control, honesty of motive — this is called mental austerity.

If a learner wants to excel, he has to honour the above mentioned austerities and try to practice these meticulously. At present, the civil society is suffering from Monophobia - fear of being alone (a disease which appears due to the dislocation of mobile phones). The Restless Mind in today's digital world is a burning problem. The minds of the learners' are infected as they are being fed unhygienic 'mental food'. Artificial silence creates an isolated life, and the condition of staying away from each other. In this perspective, apart from learning as tapas, austerity through another three tapas as prescribed by Bhagavad Gita, are important to be practiced by all learners for their all-round success.

Third Principle

सत्यमेव जयते नानृतं सत्येन पन्था विततो देवयानः ।

(मुण्डकोपनिषत् , नृतीय-मुण्डक-प्रथमखण्डः ६)

Literal Meaning

Truth wins in every aspect of life and the path of divinity moves forward by truth only.

Social Interpretation

A life which is based on truth is honoured by all. Realising the purity and importance of truth, Mahatma Gandhi referred to Truth as God. Truthfulness is Godliness indeed. Sri Ramkrishna said the person who is steadfast in truth is dwelling in the lap of God. Pure thought, speaking the truth and right conduct makes a man Rishi (Wise Man). Divinity, which is our real nature, rests hidden in the cavity of mind. For the impurity, restlessness and cynical attitude of the mind, the mind can not realise the nature of divinity which is within itself. As soon as, by regulating meaningless talking, the mind becomes calm, the infection of the mind by negative impacting factors gets reduced, the power of the truth is revealed. If a learner wants to be a man of character, a man of perfection, he has to practice truth (in thinking, speaking and behaving) and as a result of this, their life will be transformed. Hence the aim of education is to bring transformation of life - from mere animal man to a social man, and a human being to a human resource.

Fourth Principle

स्वर्थो यस्य परार्थ एव स पुमानेकः सतामग्रणी :- इति मनीषिवाक्यमवधार्य
नीचताक्लुरतादाम्भिकतादिमलिनस्वार्थसन्ततीर्विहाय उदारचेता विनयी श्रद्धावान् देशभक्तो
नरनारायणसेवानिष्ठो भवितुमहं यथासाध्यं यतिष्ये। (सुभाषितरत्नाकरः)

Literal Meaning:

The person whose interest is only to be concerned for others, he is the best fellow of all noble persons of the society.

Social Interpretation

Human society exists by division of labour and the success of division of labour depends on specialisation and cooperation. As individuals can never survive alone, they always depend on others in various aspects, so cooperation, coordination with the spirit of sympathy and empathy must be practiced by all. But unfortunately we find that society is overwhelmed by selfish fellows. Narrowness, cynical attitude, violence, conflict are the common maladies by which human society is being vulgarised.

The modern materialistic world raises our standard of living but declines our standard of life, i.e., value of life. On account of population explosion, knowledge explosion, and material explosion, man has started moving towards the wrong path by considering the material comforts of the world as sources of real happiness. Religion and morality are being threatened and the power of man is being misused. Today, the existence of a joint family is going extinct. Collectiveness, living together and working together, values that spring from the joint-family system, are withering away. Society has been suffering from a contaminated disease that is breaking joint families and giving birth to nuclear families. This is a social environment in which values are ignored, and humanity suffers.

Amidst this social calamity there are a few organisations like Ramakrishna Mission and Akhil Bharat Vivekananda Yuva Mahamandal, where a lot of youth are trying to be concerned for others. They have been shouldering their accountability to rejuvenate society by doing unselfish work, serving the impoverished section (slum children, street children, children belonging to vulnerable sections of the society, etc.) and living an ideal life silently by providing them food, medical, academic, educational support. If the Nation State is a body, citizens are the important cells of that body, and as a healthy body is needed for bright and fresh cells, a nation body is needed for enlightened and committed citizens. The way to becoming an enlightened citizen involves not only developing cognitive abilities but also expanding the heart and developing a sense of connection with others, feeling for others. In the classical book 'Dharma and Religion' (1915, p. 74) by Sister Nivedita, in the chapter 'The Teacher', following the educational philosophy of Swami Vivekananda it has been distinctly mentioned that, "Education is not only mere the form of knowledge but it is the training of selflessness, that can make man a rishi."

Unselfishness is the highest value to be the best noble person - this mantra, which is derived and uttered in the convocation of our ancient Indian Education system, must be cultivated by the modern-day learners in any civil society of any part of the world, if we want to make this globe 'a land for all' and consider that 'all beings are our friends indeed' - *Vasudaivakutumbakam*.

Swami Vivekananda considered selflessness as the highest human virtue or highest religion of man. He meticulously pointed out that "Unselfishness is God".

Fifth Principle

सुपरिचालितसंहतिशक्तिरेव समाजकल्याणनिदानम्। (स्वामी, २०२२, पृ: १८२)

Literal Meaning

The strength of organisation is the only means of the welfare of the society.

Social Interpretation

This verse helps us remind ourselves that through education we learn adaptive behaviour for living together and working together. We have come to know, from the opinion of C. Lloyd (as cited in Mahapatra, 2001, p. 99), that, 'nationalism is the religion of the modern world' and the meaning of nationalism is 'sentiment of similarity and solidarity'. The fundamental component of nationalism is 'sense of unity' upon which the survival of a State depends. The words 'unity' and 'fraternity' have been enshrined in our Constitution as national values as well as fundamental duties. But in reality we are far away from the practice of these values. On account of the advancements in science and technology, our heads are being expanded but our hearts are being contracted. Ignoring living together and collectiveness of life we are living our lives with the spirit of selfishness. As a result of this, jealousy, competition, conflict, violence, regionalism, secessionist movements are taking place. In this perspective, the importance and utility of collective life, idea of living and working together which was echoed in the words uttered by the Acharyas during the convocation in the ancient Indian Education system, should be elicited and propagated. The Acharyas of ancient Indian educational schools referred to the hymn uttered by Vedic rishis:

संगच्छध्वं सं वदध्वं सं वो मनांसि जानताम्।

देवा भागं यथा पूर्वे संजाताना उपासते।।

समानो मन्त्रः समितिः समानी समानं मनः सहचित्तमेषाम्।

समानं मन्त्रमभिमन्त्रये वः समानेन वो हविषा जुहोमि।। (ऋग्वेद १०.१९१.२-४)

i.e., we will move forward unitedly, will talk collectively and will build our minds with a common tune. Swami Vivekananda said, "expansion is life and contraction is death". For bringing 'expansion' in our lives, we should try to follow the 5th verse of the Classical Convocation as the magna carta of united life.

Life is a struggle; life is a great battle, full of challenges. A fully bloomed and excellent being alone can boldly and bravely fight this battle and overcome the challenges of life. Such a person alone can enjoy the pleasure of life. The values offered by the Convocation of the ancient Indian Education system have immense importance in the lives of the current generation learners too. It is also to be mentioned here that these values are already within us. If one wants to excel in life, one has to honour these values which are dormant inside invisible cavities of the mind and the brain. Such values are neither 'taught' nor 'brought' but 'caught', and are to be carried out throughout life.

FINDINGS

- (1) Pedagogy is the 'Science of Teaching' which is a process of contribution to the growth of knowledge, skill, literature or art, etc. It is an activity to train the students for creative thinking to face the challenges in their future life.

- (2) In the Classical Indian Education System of the Upanishadic age, a unique pedagogical concept was there. In accordance with the state of mind to which the learners belonged, different teaching methods were applied by the teachers. The Upanishadic system of teaching was done at that time at all the three levels viz, memory, understanding and reflective. The emphasis was laid on discussions, questioning, induction and deduction. Commentaries, illustrations, descriptions, narrations and practical demonstrations could be easily inferred from the text of Upanishads.
- (3) Values offered by the Acharyas (Teachers) in the time of Convocation were the guiding principles for being an enlightened social being.
- (4) Democratic principles and the norms of harmony of life were practiced in the Classical Education System of India.
- (5) Ancient Indian Education System gifted 'Ethology' (Science of Character) to human society for making it free from shortcomings.
- (6) Today teachers should help the learners to understand the current-day education system with reference to the past.

CONCLUSION

The Indian Education System has a great and glorious past, in which, the quest of knowledge was the virtue or 'dharma' of learners. Teachers were ever curious but never satisfied. They used to take teaching as the sacred task of life, and had deep compassion for their pupils. There was no monetary relation between the two units. The fundamental principle of education was to modify the behavior of the learners, not merely achieving a certain amount of knowledge. Pedagogy was imparted according to the interest and needs of the learners. The teacher, i.e., the Acharya, was himself a curriculum. His behavioural demonstration was the chief concern of learning for his learners. As a result, Ethology (science of character) was revealed across the course of studies, and the system of education produced learners who were not only learned but also responsible and committed citizens to the advancement of society. Today, when we are habituated to follow Western Pedagogy ignoring our indigenous pedagogy, we should look back to our past glorious education system and draw a set of inspiring principles which are ever-relevant, and apply the same in the modern education.

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